

A new Communication Law in Ecuador?

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After the first round of elections in 2025, and after the statements of Assemblyman Xavier Lasso to “work on a Communication Law”, concerns have circulated because a sanctioning and controlling spirit of the press, radio and television would be recovered.

Although it is understandable that imposing a rule that is contrary to international treaties generates alarm, it is also true that it is necessary to discuss how to deal with the concentration of social network platforms or the irruption of Generative Artificial Intelligence, among other issues that mark the agendas of media regulation.

The purpose of organic laws is to protect fundamental rights; therefore, the exercise of communication must contribute to human promotion. In addition, the technological irruption requires constant revisions to take advantage of new tools or to prevent their effects from restricting freedom of expression.

Do Ecuadorians have minimum conditions to receive information or express their opinions? Does the entire national territory receive analogue and digital communication signals? Do people have sufficient skills for a minimally critical consumption of the messages that circulate through social networks? How do public media help to meet the needs of the inhabitants? Before whom, and how, can citizens ask for reparations for false messages that affect them?

Like the above, there are more questions whose answers are slow in coming, and surprisingly these absences constitute a breach of the Constitution because the right to communication is not protected.

Perhaps the concern should not be a new gag law, but to question how not to continue to alienate people from quality communication, otherwise the gap between info rich and info poor will continue.